

Records Management Practice in Ministry of Mineral Resources, Bayelsa State

Ogbara, I. Catherine (Ph.D, cIn)

University Library, University of Africa, Toru-Orua
izibedekilibo@gmail.com

Jonathan, Elizabeth Ayebapreye (mnl)

University Library, University of Africa, Toru-Orua
jonathanelizabeth@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study investigated “Records Management Practice in Ministry of Mineral Resources, Bayelsa State”. It adopted descriptive research survey with a population of 27 staff at federal ministry of mineral resources Bayelsa State. Total enumeration sampling technique was used to select all the respondents. Questionnaire titled Records Management in Ministry of Mineral Resources (RMMMR) was used to gather the data. 27 copies of the instrument were distributed with the help of a research assistant only 23 copies were found valid for analysis. The data were analyzed using simple percentages presented in charts. The findings showed that the Ministry of mineral resources in Bayelsa state created and kept records on the types of resources exploited, records of LGAs containing minerals, records of area exploited, administrative records, legal records/ministry Act, financial/accounting records and records of illegal exploitation. Records were stored manually and electronically. Staff lacked the skills to manage the ministry records. The challenges faced included lack of policy, lack of procedure for managing records, inadequate storage facilities, lack of skilled staff, lack of database and nonchalant attitude of staff. It was recommended that the ministry should use a spatial database that will help to keep a better record of the mineral resources in the country. Also, staff should be trained.

Keywords: Records; Records Management; Ministry of Mineral Resources.

Introduction

Mineral resources refer to natural resources that exist in the ground or on the surface in the form of natural mineral deposits or useful minerals in either solid, liquid or gaseous status which exist underground or on the ground and may be extractable in a present or future time. Mining wastes which may be re-exploited later are also deemed mineral *resources*. Mineral resources are non-living naturally occurring matters which comprises solid inorganic matter or petrified organic substance including industrial mineral, valuable metals, which can be discovered both in and on the earth's crust in such form and quantity and of such a grade or quality that it has realistic expectations for cost-effective extraction. Geological instruments like aerial magnetometer, scintillation counter, bearing plate, rock hammer, blasting cap, auger, Geiger counter, compass and x-ray fluorescence spectrometer are used to generate geological evidences that help determine the location, quality, geological characteristics and their abundance in nature (Onuiri, Ogbonna, Alli-Shehu & Maduakolam, 2015)

There are over 40 different types of minerals in Nigeria. Every state in Nigeria has at least one mineral resource and some mineral resources can be found in more than one state. For instance, lead/zinc can be found in Bayelsa, Abia, Abuja, Imo, Enugu, Ebonyi, Cross-River, Benue, Anambra, Akwa-Ibom, Niger, Taraba and Plateau. Minerals like coal, iron ore, limestone, columbite, lignite, gypsum, kaolin, manganese, barite, uranium, salt, gold, bauxite, bismuth, barytes, wolfram, gemstone, emerald, aquamarine, amethyst, sapphire, ruby and crystal exist in the country. (Onuiri, Ogbonna, Alli-Shehu & Maduakolam, 2015).

The Ministry of Mineral Resources and Energy (MIREME) is a State body which, in accordance with the principles, objectives and tasks defined by the Government, directs and ensures the implementation of Government policy in geological research, exploitation of mineral and energy resources, and development and expansion of infrastructures for the supply of electricity, natural gas and petroleum products. Ministry of Mineral Resources and Energy is responsible for sustainable exploitation and transparent management of mineral and energy resources. In line and process of their activities, records are

created and kept as evidence of works, services and subsequent guide as well as decision making. Due to their engagement in geological research, research findings constitute part of its records, also as a body responsible for the exploitation of mineral and energy resources, records pertaining to such exploitation are kept. Furthermore, its developmental and the expansion of infrastructure for the supply of electricity, natural gas and petroleum product generate a lot of records. The Ministry also generates and keep records on mine sites and deposits, operational status, the location and compilation of mineral resource estimates, records on projects and project ownership, location data, mineral resource estimates, mineral production, mineralization attributes, commodities and commodity groups, inventory of abandoned mine sites, mine operators and contact addresses and mining proposals for development and mineral production statistics. Tasmania Archive Heritage (n.d) included natural gas, crude oil, silica sand and Agro raw materials such as cassava, fish, oyster, shrimps, cocoyam, plantain, cane wood, rice, sugarcane, sea foods, maize, timber as parts of resources explored and exploited by the Ministry of Mineral Resources.

These records are vital tools to the staff and management of the Ministry therefore, the need for proper management. This is because records management enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of any organization. Tasmanian Archive and Heritage (n.d) opined that daily operations are the basis for the development of a procedure manual for the records team and promote consistency of process, and information sharing, in the event of new staff, volunteers or contractors. Therefore, records should be regularly reviewed and updated as required to allow for organizational and procedural change. Whether paper or electronic record-keeping systems are in place, key functions include record identification, record capture, registration, indexing, classification, file creation and closure, distribution & tracking, search & retrieval, access, security, storage, scheduling, retention & disposal, records transfer, e-discovery & Disposal Freezes, vital records, disaster management and reporting on activities, performance and compliance. Often times these measures are not taken and it impedes the efficiency of records. Hence, the need to study records management practices in the ministry of mineral resources. The study will assist government and the staff of the ministry of

mineral resources to know the types of records to keep the storage facilities to employ and the right skills to acquire.

Statement of the Problem

Nigerian minerals and mining act, 2007 empowers the ministry of mineral resources to search, explore and exploit all types of minerals resources on the land including natural gas, crude oil, gas, agro raw materials such as cassava, rice, yam, etc. by the function of the ministry, they generate documents such as registers and fees including other activities that may arise such as when there is illegal mining. All these constitute records that the ministry generates and keep. These records are important for the decision making and smooth running of the ministry. When these records are not properly managed and kept it affects the smooth running of the ministry and gives room for corruption and uncertainty. Ministries are therefore, expected to manage their records effectively but this is not always the case in Nigeria particularly in Bayelsa State. The study therefore, sought to investigate “Records Management Practice in Ministry of Mineral Resources, Bayelsa State.

Objective of the study

The main objective of the study is to investigate records management practice in the Ministry of Mineral resources Bayelsa State. The specific objectives are to:

1. identify types of Records created and kept at the Ministry of Mineral Resources
2. investigate methods of Records Keeping at Ministry of Mineral Resources, Bayelsa State
3. determine the staff skills and knowledge about records management at the Ministry of Mineral Resources Bayelsa State.
4. ascertain challenges faced in the management of Records at the Ministry of Mineral Resources in Bayelsa state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study

1. what types of records are created and kept at the Ministry of Mineral Resources, Bayelsa State?
2. what are methods used in keeping records at the Ministry of Mineral Resources, Bayelsa State?
3. what are skills and knowledge of staff about records management at the Ministry of Mineral Resources Bayelsa State?
4. what are the Challenges faced in records management at the Ministry of Mineral Resources, Bayelsa State?

History of Bayelsa state Ministry of Mineral Resources

The ministry was created March 2014, from the ministry of power during the administration of Honorable Henry Seriake Dickson, then Governor of Bayelsa State. The ministry was charged with a mission to exploit and explore the solid mineral deposit, oil and gas in the state. The ministry has seven departments which are: petroleum department, solid mineral department, geological and survey department, community interface department, planning research department and statistics (PRS) department, administrative department, human resource management and financial\ account department. These various departments discharge different functions. For example, petroleum department are charged with the responsibility to advice the commissioner and governor on all matters and to furnish the ministry with information regulating the oil wells, production rate of oil and gas in the state.

Solid mineral department ascertains the solid mineral deposit in the state and to advice the governor on how to utilize such solid mineral for the development of the state. Geological and survey department, their major function is survey work, to supply information on solid mineral oil and gas deposit in the state. Community interface: their main function is to settle disputes (IOCs) international oil company and their host community. They also supervise GMoU general memorandum of understanding and to make sure that there is peaceful coexistence between host communities and oil companies. Administrative department: their major functions are to take care of the day-to-day activities of the ministry. Financial and account department: financial and account, is charged with the responsibilities of taking care of any matter relating to financial

issues. Human resource management: they are charged with the strategic approach to the effective management of people in the ministry etc. Each of these departments has various heads.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Records and Records Management

A record is a document that memorizes and gives objective evidence of activities performed by a business, the occasions that the activities happened, results accomplished or received by an organization in the cause of transacting business or in pursuance of its legal commitments. The Archives and Records Management Association (as cited in Nyaga, Kamau & Kemoni, 2020) stated that the proof of what an institution does is expressed by records. Furthermore, records capture exercises and transactions carried out by a business amongst them contract arrangements, business correspondence, personnel records, financial statement to mention but a few. It is a proof that an event occurred, irrespective of the medium, format or attributes. A record can be created or received by an organization in order to comply or pursue a legal obligation in the course of transacting business. Records can exist in a variety of formats; for example, they can either be tangible items such as paper documents, birth (Nyaga, Kamau & Kemoni, 2020)

Records are documentary evidence of routine transactions made or received by an organization in pursuit of its legal obligations irrespective of the physical form or characteristics. They are category of information identified by the particular functions they perform in support of business, accountability and cultural heritage. They confirm who did what, where, and when. Therefore, records management is making and maintaining complete, accurate and reliable evidence of official business in the form of recorded information. Records are important to the administration of government institutions, because they contain the necessary information that helps government programmes function effectively (Alegbeleye & Chilaka, 2019).

According to Igbokwe-Ibeto (2013) records management is an activity embarked on for the sole purpose of keeping track of information which can be used as a proof or evidence of an activity or action undertaken and a basis on which future decisions are made. Record management is maintaining the records of an organization from the time they are created up to their eventual disposal; this may include classifying, storing, securing, archiving, and destroying records

Types of Records created and kept at the Ministry of Mineral Resources

Record creation simply refers to the establishment of records. Records are not borne out of thin air;

they are created from actual happenings. Record creation stage is the first stage in the life cycle of records management, and as such care should be taken, because the level of success attained in this stage may affect the other stages of the record life cycle. The creation of records must be properly captured on an appropriate medium after creation so that they are readily available for institutional support.

In government ministries, like the Ministry of Mineral Resources a record is either received or created, the creation of a record starts when a letter is produced, an e-mail is written, a form is

completed or a pamphlet is printed in any government ministry or nongovernmental organization, as every unit of the ministry needs records in order to attain efficiency and effectiveness (Alegebeye & Chilaka, 2019). Kullabs (2020) identified various types of records as correspondence records, accounting and financial records, legal records, personnel records, progressive records and miscellaneous records. Furthermore, correspondence records may be created inside the office or may be received from outside the office. Ministry of Mineral Resources generates records from its activities. These records could be generated based on daily routine or notable achievement. For example, the ministry mines different resources.

Katela (2015) identified the mining by mineral types including Gold, diamond, gemstone, salt, aggregate and dimension stone. Ikenwa (2020) listing the various mineral resources found in Bayelsa state stated that the state has one of the largest crude oil and natural gas deposit in Nigeria. According to him, crude oil which is available in the state can be used in making gasoline, jet fuel, diesel, tar, asphalt, paraffin, and lubricating oil and while Silica is used in production of glass and filtration of water for agricultural purposes. It was also posited that salt is found in Brass local government area of the state, although has not been exploited due to attention on crude oil. Other resources found in the state according to him include agro raw materials such as fish, Oyster, shrimps, cassava, cocoyam, etc. All these records are kept by the ministry of mineral resources.

The ministry also engages in environmental assessment in order to exploit the areas of potential mining. When this is undertaken it is kept as a record. Katela (2015) posits that environmental consequences should be recognized early in the project cycle and taken into account in project selection, planning, and design by preventing, minimizing, mitigating or compensating for adverse environmental impacts and enhancing positive impacts. Furthermore, Environmental Assessment Sourcebook and its updates, Environmental and Social Performance

Standards and Guidance Notes, Health and Safety Guidelines for Mining all provide technical records and guidance on these issues. Katela (2015) further reported eight Action Plan that aim to mainstream environmental management activities into the Ministries Policies, Strategies and Plans; Water and Soil Pollution, and degradation, air Pollution, disturbance of Biodiversity, climate change, earthquakes, Flooding and Landslides, radioactive Minerals and unsecured Mine Closure Liabilities should be recorded.

Methods of Records Storage at Ministry of Mineral Resources

The second phase in the records life cycle is the storage of records. Records should be stored in such a manner so as to facilitate user access and ensure that they are protected from unauthorized access, use, disclosure, removal, deterioration, loss or destruction. An organization should lay down guidelines on the storage of records including sensitive or classified records. This involves preparing and placing records into their proper storage place and when a request is made for it, it must be quickly retrieved from storage for use. For records in paper form, organizations should note that paper deteriorates rapidly in an environment of high temperature and humidity. A study by Ojo (2009) on health information management indicated that records that are managed effectively eliminate cases of missing files, increase physical filing space, reduce lengthy turnaround time in retrieving files and lengthy patient waiting time. It also assists in tracking the movement of paper records in public health institutions.

Unegbu and Adenike (2013) in their study noted that records at the Ministry of Information and Strategy in Nigeria kept their records safe on Compact Disks and flash drives. When records are no longer active that is they are no longer needed for active use, they may be stored and protected using appropriate equipment and environment and human controls to ensure record security (Chirwa, 2014). However, Nabombe (2012) raised concerns that the registries might be unable to sustain the digitized system due to the rate at which

equipment and software become obsolete and fail to migrate digitized records to other media formats such as magnetic and optical media as a preservation measure. Abdulrahman (2017) found that wooden cabinet, filing drawer and Metalic cabinet were the methods used in keeping records.

Skills and Knowledge of Records Management

To effectively manage records, there should be an established records management system, overseeing the switch from paper to electronic record-keeping, writing reports and publications, dealing with enquiries and requests for information from both internal and external clients, ensuring that data is protected, classifying and indexing records, destroying or archiving finished data/records, ensuring that records are easily accessible when needed. As a result, there should be training to staff who require access or have responsibility for maintaining records. Staff working with records management need to be patient, capable of prioritizing and possess good problem-solving skills, analytical skills, communication and influencing skills, especially when requiring colleagues to hand over records or to use the systems correctly, standard databases, software and operating systems. Wilkins (2019) mentioned understanding of industry domain, and professional or “soft” skills and information management technology skills. Praxiom (2015) stated expressed the need to be able to apply records management methods, techniques, processes, and practices; understand records management terminology; understand key characteristics of records, and understand processes and technologies used to create, capture, assess, convert, migrate, preserve and authorize records.

Kemoni and Wamukoya (2000) identified competencies and skills that records managers ought to have in an e-records environment records as information management skills, technology skills, managerial skills, and project management skills. Other e-records management skills include but are not limited to: skills to create, capture,

classify, index, store, retrieve, track, appraise, preserve, archive and dispose of records in an electronic environment. Institutional decision making is dependent on the ease of accessibility of quality record or data to support their activities. Igwe (2013) adds that librarians working in this environment must possess a high level of organizational and records management skills, knowledge of collection analysis and development, familiarity with how information resources are organized and described, establish and manage procedures to ensure access and understand record life cycle. Adamu (2019) observed that records managers have come to find themselves in a dilemma as they are faced with situations that require application of skills, competencies and technical know-how of which they have no quality knowledge’

Kavishe and Dulle (2016) investigated the preservation skills and strategies being used by the University of KwaZulu-Natal libraries in preserving electronic information resources (EIRs) to for long term availability and access. It also showed that the respondents needed training in migration, metadata and emulation techniques. In addition, skills such as data migration, data curation and recovery, metadata entry are necessary for digital preservation.

Challenges faced in the management of Records

Missouri Local Government Records Management Guidelines (2018) identified some challenges affecting records management including not having a record storage area, not devoting enough space to record storage, “maintaining” a disorderly records area, and not having a written records management policy. Mujama and Wamukoya as cited in Ogbodo (2010) opined that absence of organizational plans for managing records, low awareness of the role of records management in support of organizational efficiency and accountability, lack of stewardship and coordination in handling records, absence of legislation, policies and procedures to guide in

management of records, absence of core competencies in records and archives management, absence of budgets dedicated for records management, poor security and confidentiality controls, lack of records retention and disposed policies and absence of migration strategies for records are some of the problem facing information managers. Onuiri, Ogbonna, Alli-Shehu & Maduakolam (2015) observed that Nigeria does not have a known viable and comprehensive database for existing mineral resources, which has led to poor foreign and private investment in this sector. Alegbeleye and Chilaka (2019) in their study on records management practice at the ministry of health found the challenges that affected records management including absence of specific and general retention/disposal schedules to facilitate preservation or destruction of records, lack of procedural manuals, lack of records management policies and lack of uniform guidelines on how to handle electronic records

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive research survey with a population of 27 staff at ministry of mineral resources Bayelsa State. Total enumeration sampling technique was used to select all the respondents. A self-structured questionnaire titled Records Management Practice in Ministry of Mineral Resources (RMPMMR) was used to gather the data. 27 copies of the instrument were distributed with the help of a research assistant only 23 copies were found valid for analysis. The collected data were analysed using simple percentages presented in charts.

Findings

Research Question One: What are the types of records created and kept by the Ministry of Mineral Resource

Fig. 1: Types of Records created and kept at the Ministry of Mineral Resources

The study shows that mineral resources exploited (98%), records of LGAs containing minerals (96%), records of area exploited (96%), administrative records (77%), legal records/ministry Act (76%), financial/accounting records (65%) and records of illegal exploitation (57%). The study agrees with Kullabs (2020) that records include correspondence records,

accounting and financial records, legal records, personnel records, progressive records and miscellaneous records.

Research Question Two: What are the methods used in Storing Records at the Ministry of Mineral Resources.

Fig. 2: Methods of Records Storage at Ministry of Mineral Resources

The result shows that the most common way of storing records in the ministry is manually (98%). Also, most of the respondents agreed that records

were stored electronically (51%). On the other hand, most of the respondents disagreed that records were stored on database (75%), online

(66%) and on the floor (55%). The study is consistent with that of Abdulrahman (2017) who found that the use of cabinet was the major storage facility used.

Research Question Three: What are the skills and Knowledge possessed for Record Management

Fig.3: Skills and Knowledge of Records Management

The study revealed that just few respondents had Knowledge of agency's records and archive systems (paper & electronic (33%), Skills in the use of records management software(20%), Technologies used to create, convert & preserve record(19%), metadata (15%), Records curation and recovery(13%) and records migration (10%). This shows that the staff lacked the skills to manage the ministry records. This study is consistent with that of Adamu (2019) who observed that records managers have come to find themselves in a dilemma as they are faced with situations that require application of skills,

competencies and technical know-how of which they have no quality knowledge Therefore, Praxiom (2015) expressed the need to be able to apply records management methods, techniques, processes, and practices; understand records management terminology; understand key characteristics of records, and understand processes and technologies used to create, capture, assess, convert, migrate, preserve and authorize records.

Research Question Four: What are the challenges faced in the management of Records

Fig.4: Challenges faced in records management

The study shows that the challenges that faced the respondents included lack of policy (96%), no procedure for managing records (91%), inadequate storage facilities (69%), lack of skilled staff (66%), lack of database (59%) and non-challant attitude of staff (55%). The study is in line with Alegbeleye and Chilaka (2019) in their study on records management practice at the ministry of health found the challenges that affected records management lack of procedural manuals, lack of records management policies and lack of uniform guidelines on how to handle electronic records

Conclusion

Records are handy tools that can be used for decision making. Therefore, its proper management could help in effective operation of the ministry of mineral resources. The ministry of mineral resources search, explore and exploit all types of minerals resources on the land including natural gas, crude oil, gas and agro raw materials. Having records on their previous activities will assist the ministry for better exploitation. The study established that the Ministry of mineral resources in Bayelsa state created and kept records on the types of resources exploited, records of LGAs containing minerals, records of area

exploited, administrative records, legal records/ministry Act , financial/accounting records and records of illegal exploitation. Records were stored manually and electronically. Staff lacked the skills to manage the ministry records. The challenges faced include lack of policy, no procedure for managing records , inadequate storage facilities, lack of skilled staff, lack of database and nonchalant attitude of staff.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Ministry of Mineral Resources should use a spatial database. A spatial database is special kind of database specially designed to store data that defines a geometric space. These data are frequently associated with geographic locations and features. Spatial databases store data as coordinates, points, lines, polygons and topology and some can handle more complex data like three-dimensional objects, topological coverage and linear networks. This kind of database will help to keep a better record of the mineral resources in the Bayelsa State.

2. Adequate record of scientific research data on the mineral resources should be kept and maintained. Since information is power, having good records which provide information will assist the exploitation of these resources
3. Staff should be trained on how to manage records of ministry of mineral resources. This will enhance the effectiveness records and its keeping.

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